

IPBES VA Chapter 2 - Literature review for the philosophies of good living / IPBES values assessment (2.10)

Code: IPBES_VA_2.10

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. In its rationale, the scoping document for the IPBES values assessment established that “the design of governance, institutions and policies rarely takes into account the diverse conceptualization of multiple values of nature and its benefits to people.” In consequence, a review was conducted to look for information about values and valuation of nature in multiple sources, and considering various types of knowledge, including indigenous and local knowledge (ILK). In order to provide a cohesive story throughout the six chapters of assessment regarding ILK, the members of the ILK liaison group selected case-studies to be presented in each chapter. One of those cases is about philosophies of good living around the world, for which the search of literature is described in this report. This review was done following FPIC principles.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review for articles found in Scopus and Web of Science, obtained through two search strings, both of which were applied into each of the search engines. Results of the searches were combined and cleaned, leading to the final list of 623 records **(A)**.
- **Search languages:** Abstract/Title in English
- **Search engine:** Scopus and Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** October 17, 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 623 records
- **Search terms:**

TS= (

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ("buen vivir" OR "vivir bien" OR "living well" OR "good living" OR "collective wellbeing" OR "well living" OR "Mauri Ora" OR "good life" OR "Alli Kawsay" OR "Laman Laka" OR "Minobimaatisiiwin" OR "pura vida" OR "vida sabrosa" OR "comunalidad" OR "Sumak Kawsay" OR "harmonious life" OR "Suma Qamaña" OR "Kiwe & Sek Taki" OR "Ubuntu" OR "Unhu" OR "Umunthu" OR "Satoyama" OR "satoumi" OR "Kuleana" OR "Úxwalmixwts" OR "lekil kuxlejal" OR "teko pora")
```

AND

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY (valu* OR worldview* OR cosmovision* OR perspective* OR philosoph* OR "traditional knowledge" OR "traditional ecological knowledge" OR "knowledge" OR "local knowledge" OR "indigenous frameworks" OR "kinship" OR "principles")
```

AND

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY (indigen* OR tribes OR aborigin* OR autochthonous OR pastoralis* OR herder OR fisher* OR hunt* OR forest* OR agriculture OR livelihood OR nomad OR afro descendant OR afro-descendant OR raizales OR mestizo OR campesin* OR peasant OR creol* OR kriol OR urban)
```

TS= (

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ("buen vivir" OR "vivir bien" OR "living well" OR "good living" OR "collective wellbeing" OR "well living" OR "Mauri Ora" OR "good life" OR "Alli Kawsay" OR "Laman Laka" OR "Minobimaatisiiwin" OR "pura vida" OR "vida sabrosa" OR "comunalidad" OR "Sumak Kawsay" OR "harmonious life" OR "Suma Qamaña" OR "Kiwe & Sek Taki" OR "Ubuntu" OR "Unhu" OR "Umunthu" OR "Satoyama" OR "satoumi" OR "Kuleana" OR "Úxwalmixwts" OR "lekil kuxlejal")
```

AND

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY (valu* OR worldview* OR cosmovision* OR perspective* OR philosoph* OR "traditional knowledge" OR "traditional ecological knowledge" OR "knowledge" OR "local knowledge" OR "indigenous frameworks" OR "kinship" OR "principles")
```

AND

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY (indigen* OR tribes OR aborigin* OR autochthonous OR Pastoralis* OR herder OR fisher* OR hunt* OR forest* OR agriculture OR livelihood OR nomad)
```

- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Authors
 - Title
 - Year
 - Source title
 - Volume
 - Issue
 - Abstract
 - Author Keywords
 - DOI
 - Source
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.10_10-2020_(A).csv

Treatment applied: A screening of the records in **(A)** was performed as specified in **(R1)** which allowed to identify 235 relevant records for the literature review **(B)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 235 records
- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - ID
 - Authors
 - Title
 - Year
 - DOI
 - Source
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_2.10_12-2020_(B).csv

Treatment applied: Full text was retrieved for 219 records (either in PDF format or online access). Four of these were found in Chinese, Czech, Japanese and German, hence, they were not coded. Consequently, 215 records in English, French, Portuguese and Spanish were fully read and reviewed **(C)** by applying the codes presented in **(R2)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 215 records
- **Fields extracted (C):**
 - ID
 - Authors
 - Title
 - Year
 - DOI
 - Source
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_2.10_04-2021_(C).csv

Treatment applied: Information was analysed by applying the criteria presented in **(R3)**. Results of the analysis are presented throughout the chapters of the assessment, and also in **(D)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.10_10-2020_(A)	csv	1.1 MB	List of records obtained through the searches in Scopus and Web of Science (raw references, 623 records)
B	IPBES_VA_2.10_12-2020_(B)	csv	38 KB	Screened records, 235 relevant records for the literature review
C	IPBES_VA_2.10_04-2021_(C)	csv	301 KB	List of 215 coded records
D	IPBES_VA_2.10_10-2021_(D)	pdf	1.1 MB	Report with the results of the analyses conducted

R1	IPBES_VA_2.10_10-2020_(R1)	txt	700 bytes	Rules for screening records in (A), which led to identifying 235 relevant records in (B)
R2	IPBES_VA_2.10_10-2020_(R2)	pdf	113 KB	Codes for reviewing the 215 available documents
R3	IPBES_VA_2.10_05-2021_(R3)	pdf	119 KB	Steps for analysing the information obtained through the coding process